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The academic and professional profile of the future trainers in Galicia (Spain): characteristics and motivations to become a vocational teacher

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Abstract

Along the academic year 2017/2018, the University of Santiago de Compostela and the Autonomic Education Office of Galicia (Spain), have developed the first edition of the *Pedagogical and Didactic Specialization Course*. This was aimed to people who owns a VET degree and couldn't access to the Master's degree on Education —requirement to apply to become a teacher within the Spanish vocational training system—. A specific research has been developed from a descriptive perspective. It has been designed an *ad hoc* questionnaire that has been fulfilled by 55 students, 78% of the total population involved (70). Results show that these students are mostly men, older than 35 and trained in *Hotel Industry* or *Automotive* sector. Also, most of students coordinated this pedagogical qualification program with their current jobs. We also looked for relationships between some of the variables object of study and it was found that *sex* and *professional field* are linked.

Keywords

vocational education teachers; preservice teacher education; profiles; teacher motivation

1 The Pedagogical and Didactic Specialization Course for future trainers in Galicia

The Law 2/2006 (LOE, known in Spanish) establishes that to be able to become teacher in the secondary and vocational education and training (VET) schools in Spain, it will be necessary to have an university degree, as well as have attended a pedagogical training program with an official Master's degree level. The regulation also establishes that some professionals who have a VET degree could carry out an alternative training program, equivalent to the Master's degree. We are referring to qualified workers linked to the professional fields of (Royal Decree 276/2007): Personal Appearance; Hotel Industry and Tourism; Textile, Dressmaking and Leather; Transport and Automotive; Wood, Furniture and Cork; Mechanical Manufacturing, and Arts and Crafts. In addition to these professional groups, we must add the special regime sports education (Order EDU/2645/2011).

In Galicia this training offer was lacking (Sarceda et al., In press), so, to answer to the social demand, a collaboration agreement was signed between the Autonomic Education Office of Galicia (Spain) and the University of Santiago de Compostela. With this agreement the *Pedagogical and Didactic Specialization Programme towards Vocational and Education Training Teachers* begins its path since the academic year 2017/2018. A training space was created which aims to train pedagogically the future technical professors of VET by joining institutional efforts.

This Course has 60 ECTS and it's developed under a blended learning modality (68% on line and 32% face-to-face). It's a modular training program, composed by 3 types of modules: generic modules —related with the history of the Education System; educational processes, contexts and people (students, teachers, families) and professional teacher skills—; specific modules —focused in the didactic process inside Initial VET— and, *Practicum* modules —students has to complete an internship in vocational schools along Galician territory—.

2 Methodology

This is a descriptive research, because it aims to approach the object of study from a perspective of recognition and analysis of reality. In this case, our object of study is the students of the *Pedagogical and Didactic Specialization Course* of the University of Santiago de Compostela in its first edition (2017/2018). The specific aims of the study in relation to these students were, on the one hand, to know their academic and professional profile, and on the other hand, to approach the overall assessment that participants make of the training. This information will allow us to establish a profile of students interested in this pedagogical training Course. The instrument used for the compilation of data was an *ad hoc* questionnaire with 45 items of different types and 161 variables organized around 5 analysis dimensions: general data; motivational aspects towards the teaching profession; self-perceived level of teaching skills development; contribution of the different modules to the teaching skills development and satisfaction with the entire Course. In this paper we will focus on analysing answers from students about the variables included in the first and second dimension —general data and motivational aspects to the teaching profession—.

The participating sample is composed by 55 students (Sarceda et al., in press), a 78% of the people initially enrolled in the Course. Sampling was incidental, since one of the last face-to-face workshops was chosen to apply the questionnaire. To analyse the data obtained, a statistical treatment was made including contingency tables accompanied by Pearson's Chi-Square Tests and directional and non-directional measures. All to determine the influence of some of the independent variables (sex, age, professional family) in others related to the profile of the students.

3 Results

In relation to the sex of the sample surveyed, almost two thirds (65.5%) were men, while women represented 34.5%. Both men and women, most of them have more than 35 years (67.3% of the total), and it is noteworthy that the youngest students —between 20 and 25 years old— are only men (12.7% of the sample). Attending to the professional group of their VET diploma, there is a clear predominance of Hotel Industry and Tourism (27.3%), Personal Appearance (25%) —where all students are women— and Transport and Automotive (20%). With less presence there are graduates of Mechanical Manufacturing (14.5%); Wood, Furniture Industry and Cork (7.3%); Textile, Dressmaking and Leather (3.6%), and Arts and Crafts (1.8%). In all of them, the entire sample is composed of men.

Table 1 Sex and Professional Fields of students involved in the Pedagogical Specialization Course (%). Source: Barreira & Rego-Agraso (in press)

	Male	Female	Total
Hairdressing and Aesthetic	0	100	25,5
Hotel Industry and Tourism	73,3	26,7	27,3
Textile, Dressmaking and Leather	100	0	3,6
Transport and Automotive	90,9	9,1	20,0
Wood, Furniture Industry and Cork	100	0	7,3
Mechanical Manufacturing	100	0	14,5
Arts and Crafts	100	0	1,8
Total	65,5	34,5	100,0

We wanted to check if there is a relationship between the variables *sex* and professional field of the students (Table 2). As we can see, the value of $X^2=38.007$ presents a $p=0.000$ significance, which allows us to affirm that there is a relationship between the variables under conditions of dependence.

Table 2 Chi-Squared Test, directional and non-directional statistics about the variables *sex* and *professional field*. Source: Own Elaboration

Chi-Squared Tests		Value	LoF		Asymptotic Significance (Bi-lateral)
Pearson's Chi-Squared Test		38.007 ^a	6		0.000
Likelihood Ratio		46.805	6		0.000
N of Valid Cases		55	6		0.000
a. 9 boxes (64.3%) have expected a count less than 5. The expected minimum count is .35					
Directional Measurements		Value	Asymptotic Standard Error ^a	Approximate T ^b	Approximate Significance
Lambda	Symmetric	0.407	0.097	3.410	0.001
	Dependent <i>Sex</i>	0.737	0.101	4.334	0.000
	Dependent <i>Family Group</i>	0.250	0.092	2.486	0.013
Goodman & Kruskal's Tau	Dependent <i>Sex</i>	0.691	0.075		.000 ^c
	Dependent <i>Family Group</i>	0.191	0.050		.000 ^c
a. The null hypothesis is not assumed					
b. Use of the asymptotic standard error that assumes the null hypothesis					
c. It is based on the Chi-Square Test approximation					
Symmetric Measurements		Value			Approximate Significance

Phi	0.831		0.000
Cramer's V Test	0.831		0.000
Contingency Coefficient	0.639		0.000
N of Valid Cases	55		0.000
a. the null hypothesis is not assumed			
b. Use of the asymptotic standard error that assumes the null hypothesis			
c. It is based on the normal approximation			

From the directional measurements (Table 3) that we have applied (Lambda, Goodman & Kruskal's Tau), we can verify that there is a high level of association between these two variables. The asymmetric consideration of the design can explain their relationship, in the sense that the values of both variables are distant from each other in the 2 tests, obtaining in Lambda more distant scores. The non-directional measurements (Table 4) indicate again that there is a high level of association between the variables analysed, because the Phi coefficient approaches 1 (Phi= .831 p= .000). The Cramer's V Test also indicates a high degree of association, since its result is similarly close to 1 (V= .831, p. = .000). The same happens with the high contingency coefficient (C= .639, p= .000), although this test does not reflect so strong relationship as the previous ones.

With regard to *age*, as we said before, 67.3% of the sample is over 35 years old, and most of these people are linked to the professional fields of Personal Appearance and Transport and Automotive. Regarding their *employment situation*, the majority (78.2%) indicates that they currently have a job, being unemployed the 21.8% remaining. Men represent a greater proportion, both in employed and unemployed groups. Therefore, we wanted to check if there was some kind of relationship between this situation and the *sex* variable. In this case, the Chi-Square Test indicates that there is no dependency relationship between the variables ($X^2 = 2.170$; $p=0.141$). Likewise, those who were employed were asked if their job was linked to their Vocational Training diploma, to which the majority (79.1%) answered affirmatively. It was 20.9% those who considered that their current employment has no link with their training. Regarding the *time that they have been practicing as professionals in their sector* (Figure 1) most of the sample have more than 3 years of work experience (74.4%), which has a statistically significant relationship with the *age* variable ($X^2 = 30.799$; $p=0.000$). In contrast, only 34.6% have teaching experience (Figure 1), having the highest percentage of them (16.4%) experience as a teacher in private academies. These are followed by those who have worked in training for the unemployed and continuous training (CVET) and finally, by those who have participated in the IVET.

Figure 1 Professional Experience and Teaching experience (%). Source: own elaboration

Given the current consideration of the teaching profession as a sector, in general, feminized (Mariño Fernández, 2008; Carrington & McPhee, 2008; Vieira, 2015), we wondered if there was any kind of relationship between the *teaching experience* and the *sex* and *age* variables, respectively. We reached the conclusion that there is no statistically significant relationship between any of them: with respect to sex variable ($X^2 = 6.107$; $p=0.107$) and with respect to age variable ($X^2 = 7.958$; $p=0.538$).

Students have also been inquired about the level of motivation towards the teaching profession. A large majority (98.2%) answered that this is high (49.1%) or very high (49.1%). There is only 1.8% that indicates they had an in-between motivation and any one of the students pointed out low or very low motivations. With regard to the *reasons to become a teacher* (Figure 2), we emphasize that most of the answers are placed in the highest categories (quite or totally agree), except for the answers related to become a teacher because of the family tradition. In this case, most of the answers are located in the category of no agreement (65.5%). On the contrary, the variable that groups a higher percentage of the answer in *totally agree* is that which refers to teaching as a satisfying activity in personal terms (50.9%), followed by the consideration of teaching as an activity also satisfying, but in professional terms (37%). It's worth to mention that the consideration of teaching as a career opportunity was selected by 30.9% of the sample and also a similar figure (29.1%) fully agrees that working as a teacher means having professional stability.

Figure 2 Motivations of the students to become a teacher (%). Source: Own elaboration

4 Discussion and conclusion

The particular situation of those professionals who do not completed a university degree but are still needed as trainers in Spanish IVET, opens a door towards the development of a new training program to promote a pedagogical and didactical skills between the future teachers. This type of pedagogical training is necessary not only for the practical development of the teaching profession (Serrano & Pontes, 2015, p.40), but also towards the study of the characteristics of this different professionals interested on teaching. In fact, there are many research and theoretical approaches that analyse the professional identity of Secondary teachers (Bolívar, 2007, Timostsuk & Ugaste, 2009; Pillen, Den Brok & Beijaard, 2013), their expectations and motivations (Martín & Molina, 2017) or the assessment they carry out about the Master's Degree of Education (Buendía et al., 2011, Benaroch, 2011).

However, this is not happening with IVET teachers. In the international field, attention has been paid to the teachers self-perceived needs with respect to their skills (Santori, Tacconi, & Caputo, 2015), their status and social perception (Rasmussen, 2016) or their possibilities of having a career development (Hofmann et al., 2014). However, in the analysed literature, there are only a few references that address the issue of the profile of the future teachers in a specific way—despite of the educational stages to which they are oriented to—. There are however, some exceptions focused on the demographic perspective (Zumwalt & Craig, 2009, Feistritz, 2011) or the profile based on sociocultural values and motivations to be a teacher (Richardson & Walth, 2006). The specific profile that we can draw within this paper about the future IVET teacher, indicates that the typical person is a man with more than 35 years old, with an access qualification probably linked to Hotel Industry and Tourism or Transport and Automotive. Furthermore, he usually balances the pedagogical Course with a job and he has a professional experience of more than 3 years.

We also analysed if there are significant dependency relationships between the variables studied, obtaining positive results with regard to the professional field and the student's sex, as well as professional experience and age. In addition, what is stated in this research matches with the traditional sexual division of labour applied to VET (Mariño Fernández, 2008). This persistent clear gender bias in VET—horizontal segregation—may have its origin in vocational choice (Volodina & Nagy, 2016), but it also seems to be clearly related to the segmentation of the labour market according to sex (Mariño Fernández, Rial Sánchez & Rego-Agraso, 2011; Haasler, 2015). In this sense, it seems necessary to design educational actions in VET framework, to for example, bring women closer to careers related to STEM (Makarova, Aeschlimann & Herzog, 2016, Volodina & Nagy, 2016).

In addition, the future IVET teacher is not a person who has, in general, previous teaching experience. This reality contrasts with a high or very high motivation towards the teaching profession. We could say that these are people who want to redirect their career (Berger & D'Ascoli, 2012) towards teaching. The reasons given to make this decision had to do with the gratification that the exercise of teaching supposes at a personal and professional level, which may be related to the self-perception of their teaching skills or with the value attributed to the teaching fact (Richardson & Watt, 2006). The students also linked the teaching activity with a stable professional opportunity and this is a recurrent point in several researches on teacher motivations (Kyriacou, Hultgren & Stephens, 1999, Richardson & Watt, 2005).

The organization of a pedagogical and didactic training aimed at professionals who do not have a previous university degree is a challenge for Spanish Universities, due to its complexity and because of the access profile of the students—in many cases, far away from the strictly academic uses—. One of the keys seems to be to know in depth these students and their motivations, in order to administer a training that meets their expectations and, at the same time, grant them an authorization for teaching. They must know the IVET system, be able to analyze its framework of action and also to understand the challenges that this educational stage has ahead.

References

- Barreira, E. M. & Rego-Agraso, L. (in press). O curso de especialização em formação pedagógica e didáctica do profesorado técnico de formação profissional: perfil de acesso do aumnado. *20º Congresso Internacional de Formação para o Trabalho Norte de Portugal/Galiza. Trabalho digno, emprego sustentável e desenvolvimento humano: desafios da/para formação* (28/06/2018-29/06/2018). Oporto (Portugal).

- Benaroch, A. (2011). Diseño y desarrollo del Máster en profesorado de educación secundaria durante su primer año de implantación. *Revista Eureka sobre Enseñanza y Divulgación de las Ciencias*, 8 (1), 20-40
- Berger, J.-L. & D'Ascoli, Y. (2012). Becoming a VET teacher as a second career: Investigating the determinants of career choice and their relation to perceptions about prior occupation. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Teacher Education*, 40, 317–341. doi: 10.1080/1359866X.2012.700046.
- Bolívar, A. (2007). La formación inicial del profesorado de secundaria y su identidad profesional. *Estudios sobre Educación*, 12, 13-30.
- Buendía, L., Berrocal, E., Olmedo, E.M., Pegalajar, M., Ruiz, M.A. & Tomé, M. (2011). Valoración por parte del alumnado de las competencias que se pretenden conseguir con el Máster universitario de profesorado de educación secundaria obligatoria, bachillerato, formación profesional y enseñanza de idiomas. *Bordón*, 63 (3), 2011, 57-74.
- Carrington, B., & McPhee, A. (2008). Boys' 'underachievement' and the feminization of teaching. *Journal of Education for Teaching*, 34 (2), 109–120. doi: 10.1080/02607470801979558.
- Feistritzer, C.E. (2011). *Profile of teachers in the US 2011*. Washington D.C.: National Center for Education Information.
- Haasler, S. (2015). Still a perfect model? The gender impact of vocational training in Germany. *Journal of Vocational Education & Training*, 67(1), 78-92. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13636820.2014.922118>
- Hofmann, C., Stalder, B.E., Tschan, F. & Häfeli, K. (2014). Support from teachers and trainers in Vocational education and training: The pathways to career aspirations and further career development. *International Journal for Research in Vocational Education and Training (IJRVET)*, 1(1), 1-20. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13152/IJRVET.1.1.5>
- Kyriacou, C., Hultgren, A. & Stephens, P. (1999) Student teachers' motivation to become a secondary school teacher in England and Norway. *Teacher Development*, 3 (3), 373-381. doi: 10.1080/13664539900200087
- Law 2/2006, of May 3rd, of Education. *Boletín Oficial del Estado (BOE)*, No. 106, 04/05/2006
- Makarova, E., Aeschlimann, E. & Herzog, W. (2016). Why is the pipeline leaking? Experiences of young women in STEM vocational education and training and their adjustment strategies. *Empirical Research in Vocational Education and Training*, 8 (2), 1-18. doi: 10.1186/s40461-016-0027-y
- Mariño Fernández, R. (2008). Análisis de la trayectoria formativa de la mujer en las ramas industriales de la F.P. en Galicia y su inserción socio-laboral (doctoral thesis). Santiago de Compostela: Universidade de Santiago de Compostela.
- Mariño Fernández, R., Rial Sánchez, A. & Rego-Agraso, L. (2011). La situación de la mujer como alumna de formación profesional inicial y como profesional en el mercado laboral. *Revista Iberoamericana de Educación*, 54 (6), 1-14.
- Martín, A. & Molina, E. (2017). Motivaciones hacia la formación inicial pedagógica en estudiantes del Máster en Educación Secundaria de la Universidad de Granada. *Revista Española de Orientación y Psicopedagogía (REOP)*, 28, (3), 63 – 81.
- Order EDU/2645/2011, of September, 23rd that establishes the equivalent pedagogical and didactic training required for those persons who, being in possession of a degree declared equivalent for the purposes of teaching, cannot complete Master's studies. *Boletín Oficial del Estado (BOE)*, No. 240, 05/10/2011.
- Pillen, M.T., Den Brok, P.J. & Beijjaard, D. (2013). Profiles and change in beginning teachers' professional identity tensions. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 34, 86-97.

- Rasmussen, C. (2016). *Improving the quality, capability and status of the VET teacher workforce*. Melbourne: International Specialised Skills Institute.
- Royal Decree 276/2007, of February, 23rd, that approves the Regulation of entry, access and acquisition of new specializations in the teaching bodies referred to in the Organic Law 2/2006, of May 3rd, of Education. *Boletín Oficial del Estado (BOE)*, No. 53, 02/03/2007.
- Richardson, P.W. & Watt, H.H.G. (2005). 'I've decided to become a teacher': Influence's on career change. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 21, 475–489.
- Richardson, P. W. & Watt, H. M. G. (2006). Who chooses teaching and why? Profiling characteristics and motivations across three Australian universities. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Teacher Education*, 34(1), 27–56.
- Santori, R., Tacconi, G. & Caputo, B. (2015). Competence-based analysis of needs in VET teachers and trainers: an Italian experience. *European Journal of Training and Development*, 39 (1), 22– 42 Retrieved from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/EJTD-09-2013-0089>
- Sarceda-Gorgoso, C., Rodicio-García, M.L., Caldeiro-Pedreira, M. C. & Mariño Fernández, R. (in press). Percepción del futuro profesorado técnico de Formación Profesional sobre su formación pedagógica y didáctica. *20º Congresso Internacional de Formação para o Trabalho Norte de Portugal/Galiza. Trabalho digno, emprego sustentável e desenvolvimento humano: desafios da/para formação* (28/06/2018-29/06/2018). Oporto (Portugal).
- Serrano, R. & Pontes, A. (2015a). Nivel de desarrollo de las competencias y objetivos generales del Máster Formación del Profesorado de Enseñanza Secundaria. *Perfiles Educativos*, 37 (150), 39-55.
- Timostsuk, I. & Ugaste, A. (2009). Student teachers' professional identity. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 26, 1563-1570
- Vieira, M.O. (2015). Feminización y «naturaleza» del trabajo docente. Breve reflexión en dos tiempos. *Revista Retratos de la Escuela, Brasília*, 9 (16), 153-166.
- Volodina, A. & Nagy, G. (2016). Vocational choices in adolescence: The role of gender, school achievement, self-concepts, and vocational interests. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 95–96, 58–73
- Zumwalt, K. & Craig, E. (2009). Teachers' Characteristics: Research on the demographic profile. In M. Cochran-Smith & K.M. Zeichner (Eds.), *Studying teacher education: The Report of the AERA Panel on Research and Teacher Education* (pp.111-156). Washington D.C.: American Educational Research Association.

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